

PRAGMATIC DESCRIPTION OF LINGUISTIC UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Annotation: *This article discusses the linguistic units in English and Uzbek and their pragmalinguistic aspects. The pragmatic features of linguistic units can serve as a sign of a clearer understanding of their meaning in the text. Differences in the use of pragmatics in English and Uzbek, their specific features are analyzed.*

Key words: *linguistics, compound, pragmalinguistic, words, phrases, implication, proposition, intention.*

The process of human communication is much more complicated, because it involves not only the vocabulary of the speaker, but also his worldview, factors such as knowledge and skills acquired, social status, time, place and situation in which communication takes place are also important. The circumstances in which compound nouns are used by whom and for what purpose determine their “pragmatic potential” in context.

Any compound word can be transformed into a sentence using a simple linguistic operation, more precisely, a transformation. For example:

rain water This water is from the rain. This water is the result of the rain.

Old-maid This maid is old.

Backwoodsman This man lives in the far backwoods.

Therefore, we need to talk about some features of the sentence. The structure of a sentence is compared to the structure of a piece of being represented by that sentence. The basic unit of syntax is that the sentence represents some event in the being, a part of the being, reflected in the human mind: the child is playing, the apple has blossomed. The part of speech shows the function of the individual elements of existence in this situation: the student enters the room (the student - the subject of action, the room - the place of action, the entrance - the action). The phrase, on the other hand, represents the interrelationship of the elements of being reflected in the mind: the red flower, reading a book.

The syntax and semantics of linguistic units, including compound nouns, are lacking for a complete description of these units.

Only when pragmatics is added to syntax and semantics do language units find their true interpretation. For example, the phrase "enjoying all one's time" expresses the proposition of certain individuals and their state in a particular time and place. However, the syllable is not enough to make the proposition through the sentence clear to the speakers. To do this, the speakers will need to have a general knowledge of certain groups who are enjoying their time and of the specific space and time in which the situation of these groups is taking place. Because not all people in the world can enjoy their time. Hence, the above sentence must be related to specific individuals, specific space and time. The study of such a relationship between the proposition expressed by the sentence and the state of speech constitutes the pragmatic side of the sentence .

It is no coincidence that pragmatics has received increasing attention at a time when the study of semantic issues has intensified. As the scope of the semantics was greatly expanded, it had to be made a little easier, to get rid of the context-related part of the meaning. As a result, pragmatics was separated from semantics.

The context with the speech situation forms the basis of pragmatic research. Therefore, there is a growing need for pragmatics where the speech situation or context is necessary for the proposition expressed by the syntactic device to be understood by the speakers.

This happens in the following cases.

1. When you include non-descriptive ("hollow") words in a sentence, even, just like now. Russell argues that descriptive word analysis "pulls" semantics and non-descriptive word analysis "pragmatically." information about the pragmatic side will be essential for the correct use of words.

2. A sentence is formed in the process of communication between people. That is why in each of them the person finds his expression. Because "language is the home of being" (M. Heidegger), it reflects the spiritual world of mankind .

Words that link the content of a sentence to the speaker are also the object of pragmatic research. Inputs, words, and tools that directly represent the mode are studied through the pragmatic side of syntax.

3. Discourse that reflects the subjective psyche of man is also part of the study of pragmatics.

According to E. Benvenist, any sentence that requires the speaker and the listener and that reflects the speaker's intention to influence the listener is considered discourse .

Pragmatics also includes issues such as the types of sentences according to the purpose of expression, the relationship between objective content and the form expressed, the effect of the state of inequality between form and content in speech:

4. Speech habits (etiquette), which show the relationship between "I" and "others", methods of expression of respect are also areas of study of pragmatics.

5. The most important area of study of pragmatics is presupposition. For example, even if it is known to others that someone came from the phrase “Ahmad has come”, the information about what kind of person Ahmad is, where he came from and for what purpose will be obscure. The fact that the speaker and the listener already have such information, a source of general knowledge, ensures that the information that is directly expressed is understandable to the speakers.

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